

Adsorption of amphiphilic grafted polymers as polymer corrosion inhibitors: insights from mesoscopic simulations

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1 Introduction

Polymer adsorption onto surfaces is of great importance for applications such as drug delivery^{12,23}, heavy-duty protective coating against corrosion³⁶ and tissue replacement⁴⁰. Furthermore, complex copolymer-like molecules offer additional possibilities, such as the case of interaction chromatography, where the difference in adsorption strength of the individual compounds of a mixture is the basis of the separation mechanism¹⁶. A combination of size-exclusion-based and interaction-based chromatography has been found to display high separation efficiency^{1,4,24,30,32}. The phase behaviour of linear^{22,31} and grafted^{10,17,18,42} polymer chains near absorbing walls has been largely studied, finding collapsed and globular conformations, on top of the adsorbed/desorbed regimes.

Amphiphilic polymers in solution have been shown to self-assemble into a rich phase behaviour due to the different interaction of the solvent with the backbone and the side chains of the molecule.^{3,24,26,37,39} In bulk, *i.e.* in the absence of walls, their phase behaviour has been studied theoretically using scaling theory⁵ and via molecular dynamics^{9,20}. The amphiphilic polymer can self-assemble into configurations such as necklace of starlike micelles or necklace of so-called "crew-cut" micelles. Additionally, cylindrical worm-like micelles and lamellar disk-like structures can be found.

In order to protect metals and especially metal alloys, a suitable corrosion protection is needed. Ideally, Braig's⁶ definition of optimal corrosion protection can be found in an inhibitor with which the surface can be coated as thinly and homogeneously as possible. Such substances in molecular form should have an amphiphilic structure with a polar group docking on the surface to protect the metal and a non-polar remainder is as water-repellent as possible. An even better effect can be expected and seen^{7,21} if these substances are connected with each other and an even better permanent protective effect can be achieved in the form of such a polymer. Surprisingly, such a polymer can also form a protective coating on the surface very quickly.¹¹ For these reasons, it is all the more interesting to find and optimise methods to produce such polymers in the best structure. The aim is to understand what the best combination of polymeric unpolar backbone and metalphilic side chains or anchors for these requirements should look

like. Therefore we want to use and develop computer supported models to evaluate the organisation of polymers of different structure in liquid media and at substrate surfaces.

It is well known that the adsorption of amphiphilic grafted polymers is the results of an intricate interplay of solvent quality (polymer bead–solvent interactions) and solvent strength (polymer bead–surface vs. solvent–surface interactions)²⁸. The adsorption characteristics depend strongly on the grafting density and graft length.

In this work we use coarse-grained simulations to study the adsorption and conformation of amphiphilic grafted polymer into surfaces. At the mesoscopic level several microscopic details of the chemistry of the polymer chains are simplified into effective parameters such as interaction strength between different species. Dissipative particle dynamics (DPD) is particularly well suited for simulations of polymeric systems and has been largely used to study polymer systems^{14,27,29,33,35,38,41,43}, including adsorption onto surfaces^{2,28}. This is in part due to the ability of DPD to reach large system sizes and relatively long time scales. DPD allows to simulate mesoscopic properties following the coarse-graining of microscopic details into effective parameters.

2 Model

2.1 Dissipative particle dynamics

In this work we use DPD simulations to model the coarse-grained behaviour and adsorption of amphiphilic molecules. A complete description of the DPD model is shown in the ESI. DPD is a particle-based method that preserves hydrodynamics where each DPD particle (bead) can be considered as a coarse grained representation of a collection of molecules.^{13,15,25} In DPD, each bead position follows Newton's dynamics with three contributions to the pair particle force $\mathbf{f}_{ij} = \mathbf{f}_{ij}^C + \mathbf{f}_{ij}^R + \mathbf{f}_{ij}^D$, respectively for conservative, random and dissipative forces. We note that the last two terms satisfy the fluctuation-dissipation theorem and conserve linear momentum.

A soft potential introduced by Groot and Warren has been largely used in DPD simulations, resulting in a conservative non-bonded force

$$\mathbf{f}_{ij}^n(r_{ij} < r_c) = a_{ij} (1 - r_{ij}/r_c) \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1 Schematic view of the amphiphillic grafted polymer molecule used for corrosion inhibitor

with $\mathbf{f}_{ij}^{C,n}(r_{ij} > r_c) = 0$. The cut-off distance r_c determines the range of the DPD interaction. All forces act in the direction of the interparticle unit vector $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij} = (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j)/r_{ij}$, where \mathbf{r}_i denotes the position of the i th bead. The maximum interaction strength a_{ij} characterises the repulsive interaction between beads. Although all interactions described via equation 1 are repulsive, beads can experience an effective attraction if the interaction strength $a_{i \neq j}$ between two beads of different species is weaker than the interaction strength between like species a_{ii} . By setting a_{ij} for dissimilar species we tune the interaction between the material elements of the simulation.

In order to construct the amphiphillic molecule, a conservative bonded interaction is introduced as a harmonic spring potential resulting in a force acting between two consecutive beads in a polymer chain,

$$f_{i,i+1}^{C,b} = -K(r_{i,i+1} - r_0)\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{i,i+1} \quad (2)$$

where K and r_0 are the spring constant and the equilibrium distance, respectively. In this work we select $K = 4.0$ and $r_0 = 0$, in accordance to standard values in coarse-grained polymer simulations^{8,28}.

DPD units are used throughout this manuscript, expressing length and energy in units of r_c and $k_B T$, respectively. In order to relate the DPD potential units to experimental values, we can make use of the correspondence by Groot and Warren to relate the DPD parameters a_{ij} with the Flory-Huggins parameter χ_{ij} describing the interaction between DPD beads as

$$\chi_{ij} \approx 0.286\Delta a_{ij} \quad (3)$$

as shown in equation 24 from Ref.¹⁵, where $\Delta a_{ij} = a_{ij} - a_{ii}$; $a_{ii} = a_{jj} = 75/\rho$ and ρ is the system number density. Eq. (3) holds for $\rho = 3$, which is also employed in this work. Values of $\chi_{ij} > 0$ (strictly speaking $\chi_{ij} > \chi^{crit}$; χ^{crit} is the critical Flory-Huggins interaction parameter), and thus $\Delta a_{ij} > 0$, correspond to unfavourable interactions between species i and j (incompatibility between species i and j), while values of $\chi_{ij} \leq 0$ ($\Delta a_{ij} \leq 0$) indicate $i - j$ favourable interactions ($i - j$ compatibility). Therefore for example, a solvent i is a poor solvent for solute j for $\chi_{ij} > 0$ and a good solvent for $\chi_{ij} \leq 0$; species i and j phase separate for $\chi_{ij} > 0$ and mix well for $\chi_{ij} \leq 0$; and a wall i is lyophobic for species j for $\chi_{ij} > 0$ and lyophilic for $\chi_{ij} \leq 0$.

2.2 Specifications of the setup

We consider a system consisting of 4 chemically different kinds of beads: A (backbone), B (branches), S (solvent) and W (walls). In figure 1 a schematic view of the amphiphillic grafted polymer molecule is shown. The lyophobic backbone and the lyophilic branches constitute the molecule of interest. The molecule is dispersed in a solvent, confined between two parallel walls. Solvent

beads are nonbonded and wall beads are frozen (do not experience dynamics). Walls are placed at the top and bottom of the DPD box in the y direction, as an equilibrated layer of beads with the same density as the selected bulk one. In addition, bounce-back boundary conditions apply to the non-frozen beads, which reflect the fluid beads back into the fluid domain when they enter the walls.

The molecule of study is a grafted amphiphillic polymer with the following configuration: A backbone (A-type monomer) with a number N_A of beads, to which n_{chains} number of branch chains (B-type monomers) are grafted, with a spacing between grafted points m given by $m = N_A/(n_{chains} + 1)$. The length of the side chains grafted into the backbone is N_B number of beads. For sake of clarity, we use the following nomenclature to describe a molecule: $N_A - m - N_B$.

In this work, we consider a molecule with a lyophobic backbone and lyophilic side chains, acting as anchors into the lyophilic walls. Even though the Groot and Warren potential described in equation 1 is completely repulsive, differences in interaction strength characterise the polarity of species. The repulsion strength between same species beads is set to $a_{ii} = 25r_c/k_B T$ (hereafter we implicitly assume DPD units, i.e., $r_c = 1$ and $k_B T = 1$), which allows to define the differential affinity $\Delta a_{ij} = a_{ij} - a_{ii}$. The solubility of the backbone will be explored in detail in this work, and is characterised by $\Delta a_{AS} = a_{AS} - 25.0 > 0$, indicating the lyophobicity of the backbone when dispersed in the solvent. Contrary to that, we consider lyophilic side chains (to be precise, the solvent is neutral towards the side chains) such that $\Delta a_{BS} = a_{BS} - 25.0 = 0$. Similarly, we consider lyophilic walls $\Delta a_{WS} = 0$. Furthermore, we assume that the enthalpic interaction between the side chain beads and the backbone beads is equal to the insolubility of the backbone, thus, $\Delta a_{AB} = \Delta a_{AS}$. The side chains, grafted into the backbone, play the role of anchoring groups that permit the adsorption of the molecule into the walls. This attractive interaction $\Delta a_{BW} < 0$ will be calibrated in the Results section, in order to determine the regimes of adsorption introduced by the side chains. Finally, the interaction of the backbone beads with the walls is characterised by Δa_{AW} . The positive value used throughout this work will be justified in the Results section, in order to assure that the backbone is not attracted towards the surface. For the sake of clarity, we provide table 1 where the interaction parameter a_{ij} between species is shown.

	$\Delta a_{ij} = a_{ij} - a_{ii}$	χ_{ij}
Δa_{WS}	0	0
Δa_{BS}	0	0
Δa_{AW}	5	1.43
Δa_{AS}	Δa_{AS}	χ_{AS}
Δa_{AB}	Δa_{AS}	χ_{AS}
Δa_{BW}	Δa_{BW}	χ_{BW}

Table 1 Values of the interaction strength $\Delta a_{ij} = a_{ij} - a_{ii}$ shifted by the like-species interaction $a_{ii} = 25$, for species A (backbone), B (branches), S (solvent) and W (walls). The third column indicates the respective Flory-Huggins parameter χ_{ij} between species.

2.3 Observables

In order to characterise the behaviour of the amphiphillic molecule (adsorption and conformation) we make use of a series of magnitudes. We determine the adsorption of the molecule at the walls by determining the fraction Φ_i of beads of species $i = A, B$ within a distance $r_{absorbed} = 1$ of the wall. A value $\Phi_i = 1$ indicates that all

beads of species i are within the threshold distance to the wall.

The gyration radius of a molecule is defined as

$$R_g^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_{cm})^2 \quad (4)$$

which provides insight on the size of a molecule with N beads. The calculation is extended over all beads in the molecule $i = 1 \dots N$ and the vector $\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_{cm}$ is the vector between bead i and the center of mass \mathbf{r}_{cm} of the molecule. The conformation of the molecule is characterised by the perpendicular and parallel components of the gyration tensor, R_g^\perp and R_g^\parallel , respectively, with respect to the wall. The three cartesian contributions to the gyration radius can be separated into perpendicular $R_g^\perp = R_g^y$ and parallel components $R_g^\parallel = (R_g^x + R_g^z)/2$, with respect to the surface plane. The ratio R_g^\perp/R_g is a useful magnitude to characterise the anisotropic shape of the molecule. In bulk, a completely isotropic molecule is characterised by $R_g^\perp/R_g = 1/\sqrt{3}$.

A standard cluster analysis method will be used to determine the mean cluster size, as well as the cluster size distribution, in bulk. The determination of neighbors is based on bead-bead distance following analysis of the radial distribution function $g(r)$.

Finally, the density profiles are calculated after equilibration. In particular, we are interested in the vertical (*i.e.*, perpendicular to the wall) number density distribution of beads with respect to the distance to the wall $\rho(y)$. These curves will be used for non-dilute concentrations, that is, when considering more than a single molecule.

2.4 Computational details

The DPD equation is solved in a cubic box with size $L_x \times L_y \times L_z$ in units of r_c . The single-molecule simulations are performed in a box with $L_x = L_y = L_z = 50$ with a number of steps $N_{steps} = 10^6$. For finite concentration simulations a larger box size is needed in order to capture the collective behaviour, with $L_x = L_y = L_z = 100$. A time discretisation $\Delta t = 0.05$ is chosen. The drag coefficient has a value $\gamma_j = 6.75$ as introduced in equation S7 in the ESI. Simulations are performed using the software for mesoscopic simulations DL_MESO³⁴. Additional post-processing tools and code modifications are used to calculate the observables described above. Visualisation of large systems is done with VMD¹⁹.

3 Results

This work aims to explore the use of amphiphilic grafted polymers for corrosion inhibitors at metallic surfaces. In order to better understand the sorption behaviour of such molecules, we explore various parameters relevant to the experimentally accessible properties. The selectivity of the solvent towards the elements of the grafted polymer chain (backbone and branches) will be explored by tuning the lyophobicity of the backbone beads. Here, we assume that the backbone-branches interaction $a_{AB} = a_{AS}$ is identical to the backbone-solvent, which simplifies the analysis and assumes the same polar interaction between these species. Accordingly, we impose that the branch-solvent interaction is neutral $\Delta a_{BS} = 0$, from which we can establish that the polarity of the branches and solvent are equal. Under these assumptions and considering branch beads as anchoring groups that interact with the walls, in this section we explore the sorption behaviour and conformation of the grafted polymer chain.

This work is structured as follows: Firstly, the single-molecule adsorption and conformation behaviour is explored in the presence

of walls. This includes the calibration of the wall-branch interaction, characterisation of the behaviour via phase diagrams and exploring the role of additional parameters. Secondly, the non-dilute regime is studied where finite bulk concentration of molecules are considered. In this second part we use bulk simulations to motivate the study of the role of solubility.

3.1 Dilute regime

As the primary focus of this work is to study the sorption of amphiphilic molecules via its grafted side chains, it is essential to firstly determine the role of the affinity of the side chains to the adsorbing walls, controlled by Δa_{BW} . On the other hand, the value of the backbone-wall interaction strength is set to $\Delta a_{AW} = 5$ (which can be mapped¹⁵ into $\chi_{AS} = 1.43$ according to equation 3), in order to assure a repulsive interaction of the backbone beads towards the walls. This value will be relevant in instances of all-molecule adsorption, which will be discussed in the following sections.

Before exploring in detail the role of the backbone insolubility, we choose a weak insolubility $\Delta a_{AS} = 5$ ($\chi_{AS} = 1.43$) and explore the role of the surface-side chain interaction. The degree of adsorption of the molecule into the walls is characterised by the fraction of A and B beads into the surface walls Φ_A and Φ_B , respectively. In figure 2 (a) a molecule with architecture $N_A = 300$, $N_B = 21$ and $m = 60$ ($300 - 21 - 60$). is found to strongly adsorb at the walls with $\Phi_B \sim 1$ and $\Phi_A \sim 0.1$ for high absolute values of $\Delta a_{BW} < -10$ ($\chi_{BW} < -2.9$), indicating a strong adsorption of the grafted side chains while backbone beads are exposed into the solvent. For intermediate values $-10 < \Delta a_{BW} < -6$ ($-2.9 < \chi_{BW} < -1.7$) a smooth transition is observed where B beads are weakly adsorbed at the walls. Finally, non-absorbed molecules are observed for $\Delta a_{BW} > -6$ ($\chi_{BW} > -1.7$). Strongly, weakly and non-absorbed molecules time series are shown in figure 2 (b), after equilibration: small high-frequency fluctuations can be observed for the strongly adsorbed case, while the frequency decreases and the amplitude increases for weakly and non-absorbed molecules. The conformation of the molecule can be tracked with the all-molecule perpendicular radius of gyration ratio R_g^\perp/R_g in figure 2 (c), where we observe that the ratio grows as the particle is detached from the wall and saturates at a value $R_g^\perp/R_g \approx 1/\sqrt{3}$, corresponding to an isotropic conformation. The all-molecule R_g^\perp/R_g can be seen to change moderately within the range of consideration. This is due to the dominant role of the backbone in the conformation of the molecule, as the backbone will be shown to collapse into a micelle. In figure 2 (d), the time evolution of the radius of gyration radius is shown for relevant adsorption regimes.

In figure 3 we explore the role of the grafting density of B chains into the backbone, characterised by the spacing between two consecutive side chains m , for two regimes of the interaction between the B beads and the surface: weakly interacting with $\Delta a_{BW} = -7.5$ ($\chi_{BW} = -2.2$) (top) and strongly interacting with $\Delta a_{BW} = -10$ ($\chi_{BW} = -2.9$), which corresponds to the calibration curve in figure 2. Additionally, two grafting density regimes are considered: lower grafting density for $m = 60$ (LGD) and higher grafting density with $m = 14$ (HGD). The overall adsorption of B chains is explored in figure 3 (a) in terms of the length of the side chains N_B . As the side chains grow, the B beads are weakly more adsorbed at the surface. Surprisingly, the more sparsely grafted molecule with $m = 60$ achieves a higher absorption ratio than the more densely grafted molecule $m = 14$. This can be attributed to the crowded environment of B beads within the surface, which limits the available space for side chains to act as anchors. This is enhanced by the constrain imposed on the backbone conformation by adding more

Figure 2 Role of interaction between grafted side chains and wall for a $N_A = 300$, $N_B = 21$ and $m = 60$ molecule ($300 - 21 - 60$) In (a), the fraction of adsorbed beads of type A and B $-\Phi_A$ and Φ_B , respectively- are plotted with respect to the B-W interaction strength Δa_{BW} . The time plots are shown in (b). In (c) the perpendicular all-molecule radius of gyration ratio is plotted against the interaction strength while in (d) the time series are shown.

side chains. We note that the grafting density is, in all cases, relatively low. Additionally, the HGD molecule is more miscible within the solvent, which allows for an overall more lyophilic molecule that is not expelled into the surface.

In figure 3 (b) and (c), the contrast in the conformation of the adsorbed molecule and backbone is clear depending on the grafting density. The lower grafting density $m = 60$ molecule acquires a radically more isotropic structure than the more densely grafted molecule $m = 14$. This is largely owed to the backbone, shown in figure 3 (c), which is allowed to collapse into an isotropic structure for $m = 60$. On the other hand, for the HGD case, the constraints introduced by the numerous side chains, adsorbed at the surface, limits the shape of the backbone in the denser grafted case. In this case, the shape of the backbone and the molecule is more strongly related to the side chains which can prevent the complete collapse of the backbone into an isotropic spheroid.

Moreover, in the strongly adsorbed case, figure 3 (d), the adsorption of B beads remains largely unchanged for different values of the grafted chain length, or grafted chain spacing, but the conformation of the molecule changes radically depending on the level of grafting density, shown in figure 3 (e) and (f). Again, this is largely due to the backbone, with the side chain length introducing additional anisotropy, *i.e.*, the anisotropic shape of the molecule increases with N_B .

In conclusion, the grafted chain density plays a secondary role in the adsorption of the side chains to the surface, even though it surprisingly decreases the adsorption for weakly interacting B beads. This is the result of the crowded environment of B beads at the surface. On the other hand, the grafting density plays a crucial role in the conformation of the molecule at the surface, specially in the shape of the backbone as it collapses due the insolubility of the backbone.

The adsorption and conformation of a single molecule can be

explored in terms of the grafted side chain length N_B and the backbone insolubility Δa_{AS} . The side chain length is expected to play a crucial role as the B beads act as anchors, while the solubility of the backbone determines the conformation of the molecule. We consider a strongly absorbing surface-B beads interaction with $\Delta a_{BW} = -10$ ($\chi_{BW} = -2.9$). Figure 4 (a) shows the phase diagram of a single molecule $300 - N_b - 60$ with a backbone solubility given by Δa_{AS} . The phase behaviour at each simulation is determined by the adsorption ratios Φ_A and Φ_B as well as the gyration radius (backbone and all-molecule) and the ratios R_g^\perp/R_g .

A free, non adsorbed molecule can be observed for short grafted chains N_B and weakly insoluble backbone beads where $\Phi_A \sim \Phi_B \sim 0$. As both the backbone and the branched side chains are relatively soluble, the overall molecule remains in a random-walk like conformation. This phase is marked as black dots. Contrary to that, highly insoluble backbones are found in a collapsed micelle morphology which, at high insolubility $\Delta a_{AS} > 10$, can be segregated towards the wall in order to alleviate the exposure of the micelle surface area to the solvent. This results in a weak all-molecule adsorption with $\Phi_A \sim 0.3$ while the grafted chains are weakly adsorbed with $\Phi_B \sim 0.65$, due to the short length of the side chains. This regime is marked as red asterisks.

On the other hand, molecules with longer side chains N_B in figure 4 are found strongly adsorbed at the walls with $\Phi_B \sim 1$ and $\Phi_A < 0.4$ (see colormap in figure S1 (a) and (b)). In this regime the side chains are strongly adsorbed at the walls, while the backbone beads are exposed to the solvent. Additionally, the conformation of the backbone depends on its solubility. Weakly insoluble A beads form a *random-walk*-like structure with a preferential dispersion parallel to the walls which leads to a highly compressed backbone with $R_g^\perp/R_g(A) \ll 1$ (see colormap (c) in figure S1). This is not the case for a highly insoluble backbone $\Delta a_{AS} > 4$ where the A beads form a collapsed, compact micellar morphology, which is *pushed* into the wall by the insolubility. This is the most frequent conformation within the range of study. The effect of the backbone solubility Δa_{AS} in the backbone conformation is clear in the inset in figure 4 (a), where the shape of the backbone changes radically as the A beads collapse, for relatively long side chains with $N_b = 32$. An additional study on the role of the backbone length, in figure S3 in the ESI, shows that increasing N_A does not lead to a change in the conformation of the backbone or molecule, which remains collapsed regardless of the length of the backbone.

In order to inspect the role of the grafting density, in figure 4 (b) we simulate a HGD case, with $m = 14$. The grafting density has been shown to play a crucial role in the conformation of the adsorbed molecule, as in figure 3. The sorption diagram in figure 4 (b) shows that HGD molecules display more all-molecule adsorption (marked in red asterisks) and branch-adsorbed/globular-backbone (green diamonds) conformation within the explored parameters space. The reduction in the non-adsorbed regime (black dots) for HGD can be understood as a consequence of the increased overall compatibility of the whole molecule towards the wall, due to the increased number of B beads in the molecule. Meanwhile, the increase in the all-molecule adsorption over the adsorption via branches is a consequence of the crowded environment of B beads at the wall, as shown in figure 3. Additionally, the increased number of side chains in the HGD case limits the conformation configurations of the backbone, which in turn difficulties the adsorption of the side chains into the walls. Similarly, the increased number of side chains in the $N_b \gg 10$ case limits the conformation of the backbone into a collapsed micelle-like shape. This leads to the increase in the globular conformation of the backbone. Comparing the gy-

Figure 3 Effect of grafting density in the adsorption at the surface, for two values of spacing between grafted chains m . The adsorption is quantified by the adsorption of B beads Φ_B (left column), the radius of gyration ratio of the full molecule (middle column) and the radius of gyration ratio of the backbone (right column). Two wall-grafted chains interactions are considered: $\Delta a_{BW} = -7.5$ (top row) and $\Delta a_{BW} = -10$ (bottom row), corresponding to the weak and strong adsorption regimes, respectively, as shown in figure 2.

Figure 4 Sorption diagram of a molecule with strong branch-wall interaction $\Delta a_{BW} = -10$. The molecule is $300 - N_b - m$ with backbone solubility given by Δa_{AS} . Two grafting densities are explored in (a) LGD and (b) HGD, respectively $m = 60$ and $m = 20$. The phase point schematic representation are shown in the right, corresponding to: black dot, non-adsorbed; red asterisk, all-molecule weakly adsorbed; green diamond, non-collapsed adsorption via branches; and dark blue square, collapsed adsorption via branches. Phase points for (a) are determined *via* observables described in section 2.3, shown in S1 .

ration radius curve in the inset in (a) (LGD) and (b) (HGD), it is clear that the smaller spacing (HGD) leads to enhanced anisotropy of the backbone, with the shape of the backbone being more strongly dependent on the anchoring side chains.

In figure S2 in the ESI the sorption diagram for weakly absorbing branches $\Delta a_{BW} = -7.5$ ($\chi_{BW} = -2.2$) displays a simpler phase behaviour with only one absorbed mechanism: all-molecule adsorption, due to the weaker interaction between the side chains and the walls. For the LGD case, a modest decrease in the critical adsorption Δa_{AS} value is observed as the length of the side chains N_b is increased, as a consequence of the overall increase in the compatibility of the molecule.

3.2 Finite concentrations

At non-dilute concentrations, beyond the single-molecule limit, collective behaviour can be expected to merge, where the conformation and sorption mechanism are affected by the bulk concentration of molecules in the system. Following the parameter exploration in figure 4 we select the collapsed-backbone/adsorption via branches regime, to explore the role of non-dilute concentrations of adsorbing molecules. A finite concentration of molecules with configuration 300 – 38 – 60 and backbone solubility $\Delta a_{AS} = 8.57$ ($\chi_{AS} = 2.45$) can be explored in terms of the nominal surface coverage of B beads at the wall, expressed as $\sigma_B^* = (N_B \times \text{number of grafted chains})/\text{area}$. This quantity represents the nominal fraction of the surface that can be occupied by anchoring B beads.

In figure 5 the fraction of B beads adsorbed is shown to decrease as the number of molecules in the system is increased. This is a consequence of the crowded environment of B beads at the surface, which difficulties the anchoring of additional side chains into the surface. The all-molecule radius of gyration provides further information on the conformation of the molecules at non dilute concentrations: A first regime can be identified in which R_g grows uniformly with σ_B^* . Here, new molecules aggregate into larger collapsed clusters (micelles, as described in the single-molecule case for the blue square phase, in figure 4), leading to a uniform increase in the radius of gyration of the molecules. Beyond $\sigma_B^* \sim 3$, an approximate mono-layer is formed, while the surface is crowded with B beads, leading to density peaks of B beads *on top* of the A-rich domains, as shown in figure S5 .

Fig. 4 has shown the important role of the backbone solubility in the conformation of the overall molecule, in the single-molecule limit. In non-dilute concentrations the solubility of the molecule plays an additional role at determining the formation of micelles. Figure S4 (a) shows the mean cluster size and the cluster size distribution (b) for a concentration ϕ_m of molecules in bulk, *i.e.*, in the absence of surfaces. The formation of micelles with a well defined cluster size is clear in figure S4 (a), for $\Delta a_{AS} > 2.5$ ($\chi_{AS} > 0.7$), indicating the crucial role of the backbone solubility. This motivates the study the role of the backbone solubility in the sorption of the overall molecule.

We select the nominal surface density of anchor B beads $\sigma_B^* = 6.09$ and explore the solvent quality Δa_{AS} . Figure 6 shows the fraction of anchoring B beads adsorbed at the walls and the all-molecule radius of gyration. Weakly insolvable backbone beads leads to a random-walk-like conformation which leads to a long density tail in figure 6 (b) for the molecule species and a disordered structure in (c). As the backbone insolubility increases, the adsorption of B beads improves, as backbone beads collapse into micelles that are more easily absorbed, with the long density tails in figure 6 (d) acquiring a more bell-shaped distribution. The insolubility of the backbone promotes the adsorption at the surface

Figure 5 Adsorption Φ_B and conformation R_g of non-dilute concentrations of molecules with configuration 300 – 38 – 60 in terms of the nominal surface coverage of branch beads σ_B^* , defined as the total number of B beads in the system over the total surface area available to anchor to.

because the overall energetic gain per molecule upon adsorption increases. The collapse of the molecule, owed to the backbone, can be tracked with the radius of gyration R_g , which decreases with the insolubility of the backbone. Higher insolubility $\Delta a_{AS} > 5$ ($\chi_{AS} > 1.4$) does not lead to higher adsorption of branch beads. Instead, in figure 6 (f) the density distribution of A beads sharpens as the backbone further collapses into larger clusters, as shown in figure 6 (g).

Comparing figure 6 (d) and (f), the density profiles are considerably similar. Nonetheless, larger system snapshots in figure 7 (a) and (b) show the morphological differences due to the solubility difference, for $\Delta a_{AS} = 4.03$ ($\chi_{AS} = 1.2$) and $\Delta a_{AS} = 8.05$ ($\chi_{AS} = 2.3$), respectively. In fig. 7 (a) the two-dimensional structure resembles a block copolymer morphology with a continuous A monomer domain. This is a consequence of the competition between in-surface adsorption of the branches (blue beads) and the collapse of the backbone beads (red), into a percolating structure due to the insolubility of the backbone with the medium. On the other hand, in fig. 7 (b) the molecules acquire a A-rich cluster morphology, connected with each other. This morphology resembles the bulk self-assembled structures such as pearl necklace micelles⁵. Here, the insolubility of the backbone dominates over the entropic B beads homogeneous dispersion over the surface.

So far in this work we have focused on monodisperse molecule lengths. Experimentally, polydisperse polymer chains are often found, which may affect the self-assembly and adsorption behaviour. In figure 8 we can observe the adsorption behaviour of shorter (150 – 19 – 50) and longer molecules (300 – 38 – 60). In order to assert the role of molecule length, we consider a finite nominal concentration $\sigma_B^* = 2\sigma_B^{*\text{short}} = 2\sigma_B^{*\text{long}}$, that is, the total number of beads belonging to short and long molecules is equal. Longer molecules are found to better adsorb when mixed with shorter ones. This can be thought of as a consequence of the larger overall insolubility of the whole molecule as the number of beads are increased, due to the increased number of lyophobic backbone beads. Moreover, additional and longer side chains increase the overall affinity of the molecule towards the surface as shown in figure 2. Since the grafting density remains approximately similar

Figure 6 Role of backbone insolubility at high nominal B coverage $\sigma_B^* = 6.09$. In (a) the fraction of adsorbed B beads is shown as well as the all-molecule radius of gyration, in terms of the backbone-solvent interaction strength. The density profiles perpendicular to the wall are shown in (b), (d) and (f) for three representative values of $\Delta a_{AS} = 0.45$, 4.03 and 8.05 , respectively, while the top view of the system snapshots are shown in (c), (e) and (g), for the same values of Δa_{AS} .

Figure 7 Top view snapshots of the role of backbone solubility in a large system for $\Delta a_{AS} = 4.03$ and $\Delta a_{AS} = 8.05$ for (a) and (b), respectively.

for small and long molecules, the increase in branch beads does not lead to the crowded environment that was discussed in figure 3. On top of polydispersity, future work may address more complex molecule configurations including functional groups, in which the anchoring beads may concentrate at the end of the side chain.

4 Conclusions

DPD simulations have been used as a coarse-grained method to model the adsorption of amphiphilic grafted polymers on surfaces immersed in a selective solvent. In this work we consider a grafted polymer chain with lyophobic backbone and lyophilic side chains. Furthermore, we focus on the case of side chains acting as anchors towards the surface. This fast mesoscopic approach allows to explore the complex behaviour of such molecules in terms of both the grafted polymer configuration and the interaction between the various species in the system.

The adsorption behaviour of the polymer at the surface and its conformation are found to depend on the quality of the solvent towards the backbone of the molecule, as well as the selectivity of the surface towards the side grafted chains. When the molecule is adsorbed, the quality of the solvent plays a crucial role on the conformation of the backbone: depending on the solvent quality, the backbone collapses into an isotropic sphere or a uniform, deformable globule. Furthermore, the grafting density plays a minor role in the adsorption, but a decisive role in the conformation of the molecule upon adsorption at the surface. This is due to the constraint imposed by the side chains as they absorb into the surface. For shorter side chains, increasing the grafting density increases the overall quality of the solvent towards the molecule, as more lyophilic monomers (beads) are introduced in the polymer.

Beyond the single-molecule limit, the amphiphilic polymer has been shown to self-assemble into complex structures when adsorbed in the surface. These structures depend on the molecule density as well as the quality of the solvent towards the backbone. For the purposes of homogeneous surface coverage, an optimal regime can be identified in which the solvent quality is $\chi_{AS} \sim 1.3$. In this regime, the backbone is collapsed due to the solvent quality and, furthermore, a percolating structure is formed in a secondary layer near the surface: side chains act as anchor groups into the surface and the backbone forms a continuous network as a secondary layer. This is the consequence of the side chain tendency to diffuse within the surface, and the backbone preference towards aggregation due to the poor (but not extreme) solvent quality. Higher backbone lyophobicity leads to the formation of large aggregates of backbone-rich clusters which dominate over the side chain anchoring groups. On the other hand, under good solvent conditions for the backbone, the lack of micelle formation

Figure 8 Adsorption curves for a mixture of two types of molecules: long(300–38–60) and short (150–19–50) with a nominal surface fraction σ_B . The number of molecules of each type is adjusted to maintain an equal amount of beads of each kind of molecule.

in the bulk limits the adsorption at the surface. Additionally, the poor solvent conditions for the backbone drives the overall affinity of the whole molecule towards the surface, as a consequence of the differential wetting between molecule-solvent and molecule-wall.

We have studied the adsorption and conformation of amphiphilic grafted polymers under poor solvent conditions for the backbone and side chains acting as anchor groups towards the surface. In the context of grafted polymer blends as inhibitors for metallic surface corrosion, we find that moderate densities and moderately poor solvent conditions benefit the homogeneous coverage of the surface to prevent corrosion.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare

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